

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object

Ika laid maftuhah Analysis for **Contrasting Masculinity in War Valley Film “HACKSAW RIDGE”**

Background and Analysis

Abstrak

Despite its focus on conscientious objectors, this film provides an example of how masculinity values benefit from the relationship of power and masculinity. Mel Gibson's 2016 film "Hacksaw Ridge," tells the story of Dawes, an American soldier who enlisted in World War II and wants to save lives while helping his country. He was a man of commitment and principles, who believed that "Thou shalt not kill" really meant that no one should take human life. This belief is more important than its conformity to the company and the country. This methodology is used to obtain comprehensive data with the following stages: data reduction, data presentation, and verification or conclusion. Determination of the study material by selecting moments from the film "Hacksaw Ridge" has elements related to this research, especially humanity. The findings of this study reveal three aspects that are displayed in the construction of the meaning of humanity represented in the film "Hacksaw Ridge", namely a soldier who refuses to hold and carry weapons to the battlefield, a soldier who refuses to kill his opponent, and a soldier who refuses not to. obey orders from their superiors. These three elements show the human side of a warrior advancing on the battlefield.

Conclusions and Suggestions

It can be said that Desmond is an example of how religious values become complex and intertwined with militaristic values, and how this complexity occurs in a masculine show with the title conscientious objector. Whether Desmond is accepted as a conscientious objector or not, religion, patriotism, nationalist values, heroism, and the associated masculinity are displayed too prominently and influence Desmond's position, making it impossible to read any objections/participation carefully in films made by anti-criminals. -war. Militarism, which emphasizes masculinity and shows a patriarchal society as normal and right, is supported in many scenes through the appearance of masculinity that is prominent in the film. Desmond's different appearance of masculinity is also idealized by referring to religious values, militarism,

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and the myth of heroic masculinity. The acceptability of this show for other men is made possible not through the possibility that differences can be horizontally linked in power relations, but through the heroic struggle of difference by making engagements with the normative. Desmond's performance of masculinity represents part of the hybrid power block.

The story explores how men who take risks seeking the status of dissenters can be considered protagonists of the objections of conscience movement, which includes women, and how the "male" aspect of military service can fuel patriarchy even through objections of conscience. Desmond's character can be interpreted as a more dangerous illustration of this situation (Lewinsohn et al, 2017). He did not hesitate to accept the status of a conscientious objector during wartime, went to war to save lives, did not give up his values as much as possible, and achieved a heroic position in the eyes of a large group of people who were not opposed, perhaps not even belonging to the objection movement. conscience. As a result, it fosters and reproduces militarism and patriarchy. This replication is the only way to secure his consent.

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

Yes, there is data that is carried out in this journal using data for research material

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

Yes, the data or information is obtained through the scientific method, such as observation, and evaluation/test in order to fulfill certain conditions that must be met in order to be appointed as a research problem.

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Yes, identified through previous research mapping, this paper qualifies for originality because it represents my own ideas and thoughts.

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

This paper does not make a theoretical contribution, but it is significant that religion is an agent of anti-violence, an antithesis of war which is stimulated by wrong religious interpretations, so that many causes violence.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

The issues that occur do not contain conflicts because the lessons taken or researched are moral messages that can be practiced

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6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

The formulation of the problem contained in each research is expected to be able to understand the journal that we are discussing

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

The purpose of this research is to add insight about religious values

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

The development or shift that occurred at the time the incident occurred was the development of religion in which the wrong interpretation of religion led to violence

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

The benefit of this research for the development of science and the wider community in the future is that the community is able to present the figure of a hero in the spice of religiosity through the main character of the film, namely the steadfast attitude, responsibility and self-sacrifice.

Bibliography and Recommended Papers for

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